

EFFECT OF MUSIC TO HUMAN'S MIND

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Annotation: the article talks about music, the influence of music on the human mind and psyche, its positive and negative consequences, the healing properties of music.

Keywords: Music, mind, mood, human psyche, symphony, art, ballet, pop music, rhythm, ethnic.

Music (Greek mousiké - the art of the fairies of inspiration) is the art of sound; the term music can also be applied to a piece of music. Music (Greek mousiche - the art of the muses) is an art form that reflects human emotional experiences, thoughts, imagination through the consistency or set of musical sounds (tones, timbres). Its content consists of certain musical-artistic images that express changing mental states. Music embodies various human moods (for example, elation, joy, pleasure, observation, sadness, fear, etc.). In addition, Music clearly reflects the will qualities of a person (perseverance, aspiration, thoughtfulness, restraint, etc.), and his nature (condition).

Music inspires the whole world, provides the soul with wings, helps the flight of imagination. Music gives life and joy to everything that exists. It can be called the symbol of everything. Music is a form of art that can express the most delicate and intimate feelings in the human psyche with simple 7 notes. All over the world, only these 7 nita are used, but beautiful melodies that do not repeat each other are wound. Souls familiar with this magical world of music will always be provided with water of goodness. By listening to our national and classic tunes that are compatible with our spirituality, songs about makom, and the works of world classical composers, young people can be educated in the spirit of sincere patriotism. People who listen to such music and are accompanied by such music throughout their lives are brought up as intellectually mature people.

Musical rhythms and tones are used both in our holy religion of Islam and in reciting the verses of the, Qur'an, which is our holy book of this religion. Therefore, it has been proven even by science that the hearts of those who listen to this verse are comforted, filled with feelings of goodness, and reach some kind of divine calmness. It has been proven by experts that those who listen to the holy verses of the Qur'an, even if they do not understand their meaning and do not believe in Islam, give the same feeling of calmness to all people. This is another proof that music is a great blessing given by God Almighty.

The effect of music on the human mind has been known since ancient times. Humans used early forms of music even in primitive society. Pythagoras and Aristotle, scientists of the ancient world, were well aware of the influence of music on the human psyche. Ancient Egyptian and Roman healers used music to treat depression and stress, and to calm people down. Here again, the power of music is shown. Music is an integral part of the human psyche. A person who receives nourishment from music is highly cultured, has a pure heart, can feel beauty, and has love for his profession and his country. Competitions, music conferences, and international music festivals are held in our country for the development of music. For example: "Nihol" pageant, "Sharq Taronlari".

Music is a tool that actively develops emotions that quickly affects a person. Music introduces a person to the world of magical tones, teaches to love beauty by developing a delicate taste.

The music of some peoples is characterized by an abundance of explosive rhythmic drum sounds. It is impossible to concentrate with such music, it changes behavior, causes irreversible effects on the cerebral cortex, disrupts the relationship between neural circuits and reduces intelligence. This can explain the large number of pop music programs in the mass media, whose goal is to lower the threshold of critical awareness of new information of our youth, to instill alien values to us under the influence of someone else's music, to free them from understanding the reality around us. By interfering with the educational and creative processes, forced rhythms deprive the people of the future.

Doctor of Philosophy, V.I.Lenin associate professor of the Moscow State Pedagogical University named after Todor Dichev: "The massive borrowing of other people's musical rhythms cannot be without any harm. National melodies formed over the centuries correspond to the specific biopulsation of each ethnic group. The aggressiveness of a foreign (for example, a Negro) rhythm is a white man's destroys the stereotype in his behavior, deprives him of self-identification, harmony with the environment."

Today, the number of light-hearted melodic songs is increasing. Young people who grow up listening to such music cannot hear our national melodies, status songs, and enjoy the great spiritual world they contain.

In this regard, the following thoughts of I. Karimov can be cited: "...If a person's ear gets used to lighter, softer tones, his artistic taste and musical culture will gradually decrease, and his spiritual world will be destroyed. It is not a question of taking over concepts. In the end, it will be difficult for such a person to accept

such unique masterpieces of our national heritage as "shashmaqom" and the works of world-renowned great composers such as Mozart, Beethoven, Bach and Tchaikovsky.

The healing properties of music not only bring a person out of depression, but also relieve physical pain. Self-healing is more important than any medicine, and it is what we all hope for in difficult situations. Uplifting music encourages a person to live, rejoice and believe in goodness. It fills the world with light, and listening to it is a hobby of half the people on the planet.

Music always runs parallel to our memories, and everyone has songs associated with their childhood. For example, Moses, the son of the great pharaoh Ramses, heard music from his childhood and remembered his true origin. Have you ever felt this way? Undoubtedly, yes. Each of us has had a moment when we heard a song from our childhood and remembered in detail our happy and carefree times. Music is a powerful associative factor, because once we hear a song, we can remember it for a lifetime, and we know approximately how it will continue the next time we hear it. We cannot get such a strong effect even from a photograph, when we encounter a photograph, there is a strong doubt that the next time we face it, it will look different to us.

Perfect music moves the soul in such a way that you feel it as if you were enjoying a beloved being, that is, music, without words, bestows the brightest happiness in the world. Stendhal gave a very accurate description of good music. Someone may agree with this, and someone may not, but one thing is clear: Music makes a person live and move, and without a word, its influence on us is extremely huge.

L. V. Beethoven's 5th symphony has a very good effect on improving heart function. His "Moonlight Sonata" tends to calm people's restless nerves. The anger of the person listening to the "Italian Concerto" of I. S. Bach subsided. The melodies of F. Chopin's Mazurkas and Johann Strauss's waltzes calm the nervous feelings. P. I. Tchaikovsky's "White Bird Lake" ballet is used to lower high blood pressure in people. F. Chopin's "Nocturne in D minor" is also useful for high blood pressure and calming the nervous system. It has been confirmed by speakers that every person who listens to Anton Bruckner's "9th symphony" has a good effect on the cardiovascular organs and normalizes the volume of blood pressure per minute.

In conclusion, it should be noted that loving and learning the art of music not only has a good effect on the human mind, but also contributes to the improvement of his psyche and lifestyle. It opens the door to higher emotions.

Expands the scope of thinking. This makes people spiritually rich. And people see life in new colors and shades.

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